

Synthesis and biological activity of Schiff bases of aminothiazoles

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Manuscript received 10 July 2000, revised 2 February 2001, accepted 3 April 2001

A series of new Schiff bases derived from substituted 2-aminothiazole and substituted salicylaldehydes and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been synthesised. The compounds are found to exhibit antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Schiff bases obtained from *o*-hydroxyaldehydes have strong ability to form metal complexes¹. Thiazoles exhibit a wide range of biological activities² and therefore Schiff bases of aminothiazoles are expected to be biologically active. In continuation of our work³ on the preparation and physicochemical studies on the metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from 4-aryl-2-aminothiazoles and substituted salicylaldehydes, we report herein the synthesis, characterisation and bioactivity of a series of new Schiff bases (1-5) derived from 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole and substituted salicylaldehydes and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

Results and Discussion

The Schiff bases (1-5) are yellow crystalline solids, soluble in common organic solvents and showed sharp melting points. The Schiff bases exhibited strong λ_{\max} at ~ 410 nm⁴, and ν_{\max} at ~ 2900 (phenolic OH, intramolecular H-bonded), ~ 1630 (C=N) and 1280 cm⁻¹ (C-O) which are in agreement with the earlier reported data⁵. The mass spectra of 1, 2 and 5 showed expected molecular ion peaks and fragmentations (*vide* Experimental).

The TG results show that 2 undergoes decomposition in three stages : the first begins at 180° suggesting the absence of any water in the molecule, the second begins at 270° and the third at 420° and ends at 600°. No attempts were made

to characterise the end-products formed at the end of any stage. Compound 2 was found to be thermally stable.

Antibacterial and antifungal activities :

The Schiff bases were tested for antibacterial activity against *Salmonella typhi* and antifungal activity against *Albicans candida* by serial dilution technique⁶ in DMF in the concentration range 5–50 μ g/ml. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of the compounds were found to be 21–25 against *S. typhi* and 29–34 μ g/ml against *A. candidus*. The compounds showed better activity against *S. typhi* than against *A. candida*.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were double-distilled before use. 4-Phenyl-2-aminothiazole and 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole were prepared by the reported method⁷. The Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of equimolar amounts of *o*-hydroxyaldehyde and substituted 2-aminothiazole in ethanol. The crystals separating on cooling the solution were crystallised from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure : 1, m.p. 152°, m/z 294 (M⁺, 100%), 277 (183), 261 (70), 176 (65), 161 (70), 134 (52), 116 (48), 102 (68), 89 (37), 77 (45); 2, 172°, m/z 358/360 (M⁺, 30/28), 225/227 (18/16), 254/256 (100/63), 212/214 (15/18), 182/184 (22/15), 133 (25), 89 (18); 3, 187°; 4, 181°; 5, 170°, m/z 408/410 (M⁺, 100%), 391/393 (59/60), 375/376 (48/50), 240/242 (75/50), 182 (33), 169 (18), 164 (38), 149 (15), 127 (15), 115 (15), 89 (15).

All m.p.s. are uncorrected and all compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Finnigan MAT 1020 spectrometer. Thermal measurements were carried out by using a Rigaku TAS 100 thermal analyser.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Shivaji University, Kolhapur, for facilities and to Prof. N. N. Maldar, Dr. P. P. Wadgaonkar and Mr. D. G. Kadam for useful discussions.

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